

LEXICO SEMANTIC ANALYSIS OF LEXEMS EXPRESSING THE MEANING OF KINSHIP

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Abstract: Through this article, we have considered the semantic or linguistic point of view of the units representing kinship relations within languages, or its exceptional cases. We were able to illuminate them by studying their boundaries and types within a certain framework.

Key words: lexical units, kinship, in English, modern linguistics, correctly and objectively reveal, correctly and objectively reveal.

The study of the semantics of a word is one of the main areas of analysis of the plan of the content of lexical units in modern linguistics. F. de Saussure's doctrine of language as a system of linguistic signs and the value of linguistic units has become decisive in the study of the content side of the word in modern linguistics. The concept of value, according to F. de Saussure, is closely connected with the definition of the relationship and interdependence of language units, without which it is impossible to correctly and objectively reveal their essence. The idea of the value of a linguistic sign required the description of linguistic facts not in isolation from each other, but by establishing the relationship between units, taking into account their place in the system. The study of specific types of correlation of linguistic units of the same level in the language system in modern linguistics is based on two main types of relations: correctly and objectively reveal, which were first clearly distinguished by F. de Saussure. He found that, on the one hand, words in speech, connecting with each other, enter into relationships based on a linear nature, which exclude the possibility of pronouncing the elements at the same time. These elements line up one after the other in the flow of speech. F. de Saussure calls such combinations of elements syntagmas, and the relations between their components are called syntagmatic. The component of a syntagma acquires significance only insofar as it is opposed to what precedes it, or what follows it, or both. These relationships are completely different. F. de Saussure calls these relations associative (paradigmatic in modern terminology).

The idea of F. de Saussure about the value of a linguistic sign in the system of relations between linguistic units has found a concrete embodiment in various directions of representation and comprehension of the semantic structure of a word and the practical implementation of systemic semantic analysis in modern

linguistics. In modern lexicology, taking into account new ideas and methods, the question of the nature of lexical meaning, types of meanings, systemic semantic relationships of words, etc., continues to be studied. Generalizing studies on the most important problems of semasiology have been created. The most well-known method of studying systemic relations in modern semantic research is the so-called field approach, the essence of which is to identify semantic, as well as structural-semantic classes of words. The term "field" usually means a set of words, united by a common content and reflecting a conceptual, subject or functional similarity. The concept of a field in modern linguistics is perceived as a certain structural-semantic category that has the property of invariance, uniting the largest semantically related parts of the general language system and subdivided into private associations, revealing hierarchical relationships between its constituent smaller associations. Proceeding from this, semantic fields are subdivided into various structural-semantic associations, connected by particular semantic features. In the linguistic literature they are called thematic groups (series, fields), lexico-semantic groups, etc. more or less closely coinciding in their main (core) semantic content. First of all, the heterogeneity and significant differences in the results obtained when using this method by different researchers are pointed out. Depending on what is understood as a common meaning (content), which unites lexical units into structural-semantic fields, classes and groups, different studies yield different results of systemic relations that make up the semantic associations of components. As evidence, we can compare the results of the most famous researchers, in which the semantic commonality of the field elements correlates with the designated or general concept or with the presence in their semantics of a common semantic feature, with the nature of the reflection of the phenomenon of objective reality, with similarity or direct opposition in the main meaning, etc. As noted in studies, semantic associations and groupings, identified by scientists as a sign of the systemic organization of vocabulary, are largely unequal and even incomparable. The main thing in the study of the systematic nature of vocabulary is the nature of the correlation of linguistic and non-linguistic phenomena, in which "semantics turns out to be subordinate, not related to its own subject, goals and objectives." Therefore, one of the main shortcomings attributed by linguists, especially those who are critical of the presence of consistency in the lexicon and, in particular, the criteria for selecting a field, is the absence of a purely linguistic basis for dividing the lexicon into fields. Researchers of lexical fields are accused of that the basis for the selection

of fields is not the specific linguistic features of words, but their external correlation with objective reality, and the system is based not on the linguistic nature of words and their lexical meaning, semantics, but on connections and relationships in the material world. Many modern linguistic schools are characterized by the understanding of semantics as a special component of a complete description of a language, which, in turn, is conceived as a formal device that models the linguistic behavior of people. In order to get an idea of the language model in general and its semantic component in particular, it is necessary to understand what skills make up the phenomenon called "linguistic behavior", "language proficiency". The problem of grouping lexical units is one of the most difficult linguistic problems among others.

The study of cognitive processes is impossible without the study of the structure of the mental lexicon. Appeal to its study in cognitive linguistics is due to the fact that the mental lexicon is both a linguistic and a cognitive structure. Language is the means by which the individual experience of knowing the world is brought to the social, which ultimately allows communication, that is, the exchange of information and experience. The cognitive and language levels are not isomorphic. There is a very complex connection between the system of concepts and the system of lexemes of any language, and this connection is carried out through meaning, primarily through lexical meaning. Of course, all language levels are associated with the processing and consolidation of experience, however, it is in the lexicon that the basic concepts are fixed and it is in it that connections and relations of concepts are formed, that is, the categorization of reality is most connected with the lexical level, than with any other. Most linguists point to the complex structure and dynamic nature of the mental lexicon. So, A.A. Zalevskaya writes that the internal lexicon is "an extremely complex system of multi-tiered, multi-tiered, repeatedly intersecting fields, with the help of which versatile information about objects and phenomena of the surrounding world, about their properties is ordered and stored in more or less complete readiness for use in activities. and relations, about their assessment by the individual, as well as about the linguistic features of the verbal units denoting them. This complexity is also manifested in the fact that the lexicon is not isolated from grammar, neither from the phonetic system of a given language and the connections between units in the lexicon reflect not only the proximity / opposition of the meanings of words at different levels, but also the similarity of their phonetic design, morphemic structure, morphological categories, and the ability to form syntactic constructions, etc. In this work The

complexity of the internal lexicon interests us primarily due to the fact that, as mentioned above, it reflects ideas about the world, the classification of phenomena and objects, that is, the picture of the world. The picture of the world itself is also a multilevel phenomenon. In this work, we are primarily interested in the complexity of the internal lexicon due to the fact that, as mentioned above, it reflects ideas about the world, the classification of phenomena and objects, that is, the picture of the world. The picture of the world itself is also a multilevel phenomenon. In this work, we are primarily interested in the complexity of the internal lexicon due to the fact that, as mentioned above, it reflects ideas about the world, the classification of phenomena and objects, that is, the picture of the world. The picture of the world itself is also a multilevel phenomenon.

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